

Vanadium. Part-XII. Oxo-Vanadium (IV) Hetero Chelates-II

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Oxo-Vanadium (IV) heterochelates of the type [VO (OX) (AA)] and H [VO (OX) (Oxin)] have been described, where OX is oxalate anion, Oxin H is 8-hydroxyquinoline and AA is O-phenanthroline, κ - κ dipyridyl or guanidino benzimidazole. The magnetic moment, spectra, conductance and pH values are reported and discussed.

Oxo-Vanadium(IV) heterochelates of the type [VO(AA) (IDA)] have also been characterised where AA is O-phenanthroline, κ - κ -dipyridyl or guanidino-benzimidazole and IDA is the iminodiacetate anion.

Electronic absorption spectra have been recorded in solution and in some cases in the solid state and discussed.

This investigation comes as a logical and immediate extension of our foregoing report on Oxo-Vanadium (IV) heterochelates¹. We have discussed therein the possible routes that might be tapped to obtain the planned heterochelates. Whereas the last report concerned some very powerful tridentate ligands as the basic fabrication, we wish to describe the results that have been obtained using a bidentate reductant ligand as the basic unit.

The bidentate ligand of our choice was oxalic acid. We started with a mole of vanadium pentoxide and reduced that with oxalic acid, using a total of three moles. The idea was that one such mole of oxalic acid would reduce one mole vanadium pentoxide V_2O_5 , to produce *in situ* two moles of VO^{2+} , which would then complex with the remaining two mole proportions of oxalic acid, to form a monooxalato oxo-Vanadium (IV) complex in aqueous solution. It is this solution which

we expected to be responsive to the welcome entry of another bidentate inside the inner sphere.

A few complexes with other oxygen donor monodentate in conjunction with oxalic acid have been referred in passing² along with two bidentates [VO(O-phen)(OX)] and [VO(dipy)(OX)]³. These last two appear to be the first two examples of Oxo-Vanadium

1. Dutta and Ghosh, Under publication.

2. Sathyanarayana & Patel, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.* Indeed, after having communicated a preliminary notice of some of these syntheses we noticed that Patel *et al* have also utilised much the same reaction route for the synthesis of the monooxalato complex in solid crystalline state. However they have not done any work on the heterochelates.

3. Selbin and Holm, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1962, 24, 1116.

(IV) heterochelates, though the purity reported is questionable³. These authors³ have used a method of degradation of a bis-bidentate chelate, bis oxalato Oxovanadium (IV) $[(VO(OX)(OXH_2))]$ by phenanthroline or α - α -dipyridyl. We however, have done it rather straightforwardly. Thus the deep blue aquo-mono oxalato Oxovanadium(IV) on treatment with a mole of phenanthroline or α - α -dipyridyl changes to green and gradually a bright leaf green coloured glistening crystalline material separates out of solution. This conforms to $[(VO(O-phen)(OX))]$ and $[VO(dipy)(OX)]$ with very satisfactory analysis. We have also studied the action of guanidino benzimidazole on this aquo monooxalato complex. Our previous experience⁴ with this ligand has shown that it might behave as a neutral donor bidentate around a pH of 4 and as a monobasic acid bidentate at a higher pH around 7. On the addition of this ligand to the oxalato complex a light grey crystalline precipitate separates which had a composition similar to that of the phenanthroline or the dipyridyl complex being a non electrolyte. O-Phenylenediamine also produces a comparable, bluish green non electrolyte complex. None of these complexes has any co-ordinated water.

Instead of neutral bidentates, we have also studied the preparative method with acid bidentate ligands, such as picolinic acid and 8-hydroxyquinoline. With both these the ultimate products were bluish green to green in colour. These show solubility in water with reasonable conductance values, Λ_M for the picolinate is 216 mho cm^{-1} and that for the oxinate complex is 279 mho cm^{-1} . These lend strong support in favour of the configurations $[H(VO(Pic)(OX))^-]$ and $[H(VO(Oxin)(OX))]$. The hydrogen ion concentration also supported such formulation. In this regard, these complexes have comparable similarity with some of the heterochelates with pyridine dicarboxylic acid ligands. Their magnetic moments are also normal.

After having completed our studies on the oxo-Vanadium (IV) heterochelates based on the frame work of tridentate functioning pyridine di and tri-carboxylic acids, we desired to check up to what extent this approach could be used as a general synthetic route to the heterochelates. As an immediate extension of the work, we studied imino diacetic

acid, which has a close similarity to pyridine 2,6 dicarboxylic acid. There is no report on the oxo-Vanadium (IV) complexes of this ligand, although much studies have been done on the formation constants of the complexes that the ligand forms with many bivalent transition and non-transition metal ions^{5,6}. We therefore studied first the oxo-Vanadium (IV) iminodiacetic acid system. Preliminary studies having shown that the vanadyl complex is quite soluble, we undertook extensive spectrophotometric studies in acid, neutral and slightly alkaline ranges. In acid solution, an intense blue colour is formed, which apparently maintains the hue constant, whereas that in neutral or alkaline range con-

4. Dutta and Lahiri, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **38**, 1001.

5. Bjerrum *et al.*, *Stability Constants*. Chem. Soc. Special publication No 6, Part I, 1957.

6. Nakamoto *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962 **84**, 2081.

7. Ballhausen and Gray, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 111.

8. Selwood, "Magnetochemistry". Interscience, New York, P. 93, 1956.

tinues to change for days together. Molar ratio variation in acidic region provides a metal: ligand ration of 1:1, as was found to be the case for pyridine 2,6 dicarboxylic acid ligand (Fig 2). Because of the continuous change in the optical density values in near neutral or alkaline solutions and also because of maintaining excess vanadium (IV) in solution, we did not undertake any composition evaluation studies. It is not unlikely that the solution is undergoing slow oxidation. Further elaborate studies are being planned to throw more light into this reaction. It was the blue solution, which was fed with neutral bidentates, such as o-phenanthroline and α - α dipyridyl in one mole proportion. In both cases warming on the water bath and some concentration provided highly crystalline material. The phenanthroline complex was a very pleasing green and the α - α -dipyridyl complex was intense brown veering towards black. With guanidinobenzimidazole, similar studies resulted in the isolation of a voluminous ash coloured product of the same type as the above complexes. Their magnetic properties are indicative of one unpaired electron typical of 3d¹ oxo-Vanadium (IV) chelates. (Table VI). Our attempts to characterise products with inner metallic group of ligands, such as picolinic acid, oxin etc. have not been quite successful because of extreme solubility of the resulting heterochelates.

FIG. 1

VOSO₄: Iminodiacetic acid system—
pH variation study.
(VO²⁺)=0.04M; (I.D.A.)=3×0.04M.
A pH=3 C pH=6
B pH=5 D pH=8

FIG. 2

VOSO₄: Iminodiacetic acid system—Molar
ratio variation at pH=3. (VO²⁺)=0.04M.
A at =750 mμ
B at =600 mμ
C at =350 mμ

The electronic absorption spectra of all these above systems (permitted by solubility relations) have been investigated. In all cases we find that the solution spectra reveal two prominent absorption bands in the long wave length region, in keeping with the results that we obtained with the systems studied previously. Thus vanadyl sulphate: iminodiacetic acid system provides at pH3 two bands: 590 mμ (17,000 cm⁻¹) and 770 mμ (13,000 cm⁻¹) and at pH 8 again two bands: 540 mμ (18,500 cm⁻¹) and at 800 mμ (12,500 cm⁻¹). (Fig.1). The complex H [VO(OX) (Oxin)] also furnishes two bands: at 780 mμ (12,800 cm⁻¹) with a shoulder at 745 mμ and at 580 mμ (17,200 cm⁻¹). The corresponding picolinate complex H[VO (OX) (Pic)] also provides bands at 770 mμ (13,000 cm⁻¹) with shoulder at 695 mμ (14,400 cm⁻¹) and at 590 mμ (17,000 cm⁻¹). (Fig. III). In all such cases, there was no suggestion of a band being detectable in near ultraviolet region separately from the influence of the charge transfer spectra originating in the ultraviolet. The solution spectra of the diaquo monooxalato

oxo-vanadium(IV)⁸ provides a band at 780 m μ and a shoulder at 600 m μ , with the third band corresponding to the transition from dx_y to dx^2 orbital being overlapped by the strong charge transfer band. The complexes of the iminodiacetic acid series being entirely insoluble in different solvents, we had run room temperature diffuse reflectance spectra of the complexes [VO(O-phen)(IDA)] and [VO(α - α' -dipy)(IDA)]. (Fig IV). Both of these complexes show three absorption bands and conforms to the Ballhausen-Gray scheme. The three bands observed, according to this scheme, represent electronic transitions from (1) dx_y to dyz and dxz orbitals, (2) to dx^2-y^2 orbital and finally to (3) dx^2 orbital.

FIG. 3

Absorption spectra of solid complexes put in solution.

- A. H[VO (OX) (Pic)] 0.01M in water
B. H[VO (OX) (Oxin)] 0.01M in water

FIG. 4

Reflectance spectra of solid complexes

- A.[VO (I.D.A.) (O-phen)]
B.[VO. (I.D.A.) (α - α' -dipy)]

TABLE I

*Conductance Measurements*H[VO (OX) (Pic)] H₂O

Dilution (litres)	128	256	512	1024
λ_D	181.1	208.8	217.3	224.4
λ_{α}	192.3	217.3	225.2	229.2
λ_{α}	(mean) = 216.0			Molar Conductance = 216.0

H [VO (OX) (Oxin)]

Dilution (litres)	128	256	512	1024
λ_D	195.9	217.3	302.5	421.7
λ_{α}	144.2	226.7	313.4	430.6
λ_{α}	(mean) = 278.7			Molar Conductance = 278.7

λ_{α} was calculated with the help of Walden's relation

$$\lambda_{\alpha} = \lambda_D (1 + 0.692 \times n_1 \times n_2 \times V)^{-1/2} \quad (\text{where } n_1 \text{ and } n_2 \text{ are the valencies of the ions}).$$

TABLE II

pH Measurements

Complex	Concentration	pH	pK*
H [VO (OX) (Pic)] H ₂ O	0.005M	3.02	3.61
H [VO (OX) (Oxin)]	0.005M	2.81	3.185

*pK of these complex acids were evaluated by measuring accurately the pH of an aqueous solution of known concentration.

TABLE III
Equivalent Weight Determinations

Complex	Equivalent Weights	
	Found	Calculated
H[VO (OX) (Pic)] H ₂ O	299.1	296
H[VO (OX) (Oxin)]	308.2	300

TABLE IV

(A) *Electronic Absorption Spectral Data*
(of solid complexes put in aqueous solution)

Complex	Band II			Band I		
	$\lambda_{\max}$ m μ	wave no. cm ⁻¹	molar ϵ	$\lambda_{\max}$ m μ	wave no. cm ⁻¹	molar ϵ
H[VO (OX) (Pic)] H ₂ O	590	17,000	11.0	695 sh	14400	21.2
				770	13000	31.0
H[VO (OX) (Oxin)]	580	17200	10.0	745 sh	13500	18.6
				780	12800	22.2

(B) *Reflectance Spectral Data*

Complex	Band III		Band II		Band I	
	$\lambda_{\max}$ m μ	wave no. cm ⁻¹	$\lambda_{\max}$ m μ	wave no. cm ⁻¹	$\lambda_{\max}$ m μ	wave no. cm ⁻¹
[VO (O-phen) (IDA)]	460	21740	585	17100	800	12500
[VO (α - α' -dipy) (IDA)]	440	22720	555	18000	740	13500

TABLE V

Electronic Absorption Spectral Measurements
(in presence of excess ligands at different pH)

System: Vanadylsulphate : Iminodiacetic acid = 1 : 3

pH	Band II			Band I		
	$\lambda_{\max}$ m μ	wave no. cm ⁻¹	molar ϵ	$\lambda_{\max}$ m μ	wave no. cm ⁻¹	molar ϵ
3	590	17000	9.5	770	13000	17.05
6	570	17550	8.25	790	12660	16.1
8	540	18500	7.60	800	12500	15.07

TABLE VI

Magnetic Measurements

Complex	Dis. (Corr.) $\times 10^6$	λ_M (Corr.) $\times 10^6$	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
O-phenanthroline monoacetalato oxo-vanadium (IV) [VO(C ₆ O ₄) (C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂)]	136.74	1268.74	1.78
α - α' -dipyridyl-monoacetalato oxo-vanadium (IV) [VO (C ₆ O ₄) (C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂)]	121.46	1261.46	1.78
Oxime-monoacetalato oxo-vanadium (IV) [(VO (C ₆ O ₄) (C ₉ H ₇ NO)]	111.73	1240.23	1.76

TABLE VI (contd.)

Complex	Dis. (Corr.) $\times 10^6$	λ_{max} (Corr.) $\times 10^6$	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
Guanidinobenzimidazole mono-oxalato oxo-vanadium (IV) [VO (C ₂ O ₄) (C ₈ H ₇ N ₅)]	120.43	1250.63	1.79
O-phenanthroline iminodiacetato oxo-vanadium(IV) [VO (C ₆ H ₄ NO ₄) (C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂)]	133.22	1253.82	1.77
α - α' -dipyridyl iminodiacetato oxo-vanadium(IV) [VO (C ₄ H ₄ NO ₄) (C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂)]	119.82	1244.82	1.76
Guanidinobenzimidazoliminodiacetato oxo-vanadium (IV) [VO (C ₄ H ₄ NO ₄) (C ₈ H ₉ N ₅)]	118.81	1250.21	1.77

EXPERIMENTAL

Heterochelates derived from Oxalic Acid complex. Orthophenanthroline oxo-mono-oxalato Vanadium.—IV.—V₂O₅ (0.37 g) was suspended in boiling water (25 ml.) and oxalic acid dihydrate (0.75 g.) was added slowly with stirring, heated for 5 minutes, cooled and filtered. The deep blue and hot filtrate containing the mono oxalato compound was treated slowly with orthophenanthroline monohydrate (0.2 g) in rectified spirit (10 ml.). The blue colour of the solution changed to green and gradually a leaf green crystalline precipitate settled down which was digested on steam bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and cooled. It was filtered, washed with ice cold water followed by rectified spirit and dried over CaCl₂. The dried product was a leaf green silky crystalline substance insoluble in water, alcohol, acetone, ether, chloroform, dichlorobenzene, dioxan etc. Found: V, 15.19; N, 8.41. Reqd. for [VO (C₂O₄) (C₁₂H₈N₂)]: V, 15.23; N, 8.36. percent.

α - α' -dipyridyl mono-oxalato-oxo-Vanadium—IV.—This was obtained as a crystalline product following the same procedure as above using α - α' -dipyridyl (0.16 g) in place of O-Phenanthroline. Found: V, 16.34; N, 8.95. Reqd. for [VO(C₂O₄) C₁₀H₈N₂): V, 16.40; N, 8.90 percent.

Guanidino benzimidazole mono-oxalato-oxo-Vanadium—IV.—The blue solution containing the mono-oxalato compound prepared as above was treated with guanidinobenzimidazole (1 mole proportion) in rectified spirit (30 ml.) gradually with stirring when an ash coloured granular precipitate was thrown down. It was digested for 15 minutes on steam bath, filtered, washed with ice cold water followed by rectified spirit and dried over CaCl₂. Found: V, 15.38; N, 21.07. Reqd. for [VO(C₂O₄) (C₈H₉N₅): V, 15.5; N, 21.15%.

Orthophenylenediamine mono oxalato -oxo-Vanadium-IV.—The blue solution of the mono-oxalato compound was treated with orthophenylenediamine (1 mole proportion) and the greenish solution was evaporated to a small volume and cooled in a refrigerator when yellowish green crystals were deposited. This was filtered, washed with rectified spirit and dried over CaCl₂. Found: V, 19.28; N, 10.60. Reqd. for [VO (C₂O₄) (C₆H₈N₂): V, 19.39; N, 10.64%.

8-Hydroxyquinoline mono-oxalato-oxo-Vanadium-IV.—To the above blue solution 8-hydroxyquinoline (1 mole proportion) in rectified spirit was added when a greenish blue

solution was produced which was then evaporated on steam bath till crystals appeared. This was then cooled in refrigerator, filtered, washed with ice cold water followed by rectified spirit and dried over CaCl_2 . The dried product was bluish green crystalline solid soluble in water. Found: V, 16.88; N, 4.59. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2)(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2)]$: V, 17.0; N, 4.66%.

Picolinic acid monoacetalato-oxo-Vanadium-IV monohydrate.—The above blue solution was treated with picolinic acid (1 mole proportion) and the greenish solution was evaporated nearly to dryness on steam bath, scratched repeatedly with alcohol, filtered, washed with alcohol and dried over CaCl_2 . The dried product was a dirty green granular solid soluble in water. Found: V, 17.22; N, 4.65; H_2O (as loss at 110°C) 6.13. Reqd. For $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)] \text{H}_2\text{O}$: V, 17.23; N, 4.73; H_2O , 6.08%.

Heterochelates derived from Iminodiacetic acid complex. Orthophenanthroline-iminodiacetato-oxo-Vanadium-IV.—Vanadyl sulphate monohydrate (0.75 g.) and iminodiacetic acid (as sodium salt monohydrate, 0.8 g.) was dissolved in hot water (10 ml.) when a deep blue solution was produced. This was then treated gradually with orthophenanthroline monohydrate (0.8 g) in alcohol (25 ml.) with stirring resulting in a deep brownish solution. This was then evaporated on steam bath until crystals began to appear. It was then cooled in refrigerator, filtered, washed with ice cold water until free from sulphate and then washed with alcohol and dried over CaCl_2 .

The dried product was a deep green shining crystalline substance insoluble in water, alcohol, ether, chloroform etc. Found: V, 14.38; N, 11.88. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{NO}_2)(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2)]$: V, 14.49; N, 11.93%.

α - α' -dipyridil-iminodiacetato-oxo-Vanadium-IV.—This was obtained as shining deep brown crystals using the above procedure replacing orthophenanthroline by α - α' -dipyridil (0.65 g.) This was also insoluble in all the above solvents. Found: V, 15.45; N, 12.73. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2)(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2)]$: V, 15.54; N, 12.86%.

Guanidino benzimidazole-iminodiacetato-oxo-Vanadium-IV.—The deep blue hot solution containing vanadyl sulphate monohydrate (0.72 g.) and iminodiacetic acid (as sodium salt monohydrate, 0.89 g) was gradually treated with guanidinobenzimidazole (0.72 g.) in rectified spirit (20 ml.). When nearly all the reagent was added a blue violet precipitate appeared which changed to a voluminous ash coloured precipitate on digestion on steam bath. It was filtered, washed with rectified spirit and dried over CaCl_2 . The dried product was insoluble in the above solvents. Found: V, 13.17; N, 21.47. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{N}_3)]$: V, 13.11; N, 21.6 percent.

General Experimental Procedure: Vanadium was estimated as V_2O_5 after igniting the compound to constant weight.

Nitrogen was determined by the semimicro Dumas technique.

Magnetic susceptibility was determined in a recently set-up Gouy Balance using G.R. copper sulphate pentahydrate (E. Merck) as the calibrant. A semimicro Mettler Balance was used for suspending and weighing the sample in a Magnetic Field of 8.5×10^3 gauss generated by a Polytronic Electromagnet which was fed from the A.C. Mains via a Polytronic Rectifier cum current stabilizer.

Electronic absorption spectra were recorded in aqueous solution with the help of a Hilger-Waats Uvispek spectrophotometer using 1 cm cell.

Conductance was measured by a Phillips Conductivity Bridge and pH by a Cambridge pH meter.

Equivalent weight was determined by running the aqueous solutions of the complex species through an anion exchanger (IR. 400A Cl-form) and finally estimating the liberated acid. The equivalent weight was given by the relation.

$$E.W. = \frac{W \times 36.5}{V \times S \times 0.001825}$$

where W = Weight of the complex taken
 V = Volume of alkali required for titration
 S = Strength of the alkali used
 0.001825 = Wt. in gms of HCl in 1 c.c. N/20 HCl
 36.5 = Molecular weight of HCl.

Since our communicating these papers, Sacconi and Campigli⁹ have reported a number of oxo-vanadium (IV) heterochelates of the type [VO (X-Sal)(X-Salen-N(R)R')] with a bidentate substituted salicylaldehyde and a tridentate schiff base obtained from ring substituted salicylaldehydes and N-substituted ethylene-diamines. Using an excess of the Schiff base even does not lead to such products as [VO (X-Salen-N(R)R')]₂. Part of the added Schiff base is hydrolysed and the salicylaldehyde, thus liberated, links itself to the vanadyl unit. Whereas these mixed chelates did not result out of designed syntheses, we have succeeded in deliberately crystallising a very large number of chocolate red, paramagnetic, oxo-vanadium (IV) mixed chelates containing a tridentate, dibasic Schiff base (such as salicylaldehyde-anthranilic acid) and a bidentate, neutral donor (such as o-phenanthroline or *o*-*o*'-dipyridyl). These will be described in some future papers of this series¹⁰.

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